

Performance and Exergy analysis of TurboJet and TurboFan configurations with Rotating Detonation Combustor

Gokkul Raj Varatharajulu Purgunan^{a,*}, Panagiotis Stathopoulos^b

^a Institute of Fluid Mechanics and Technical Acoustics, Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, 10625, Germany

^b Institute of Low Carbon Industrial Processes, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Cottbus, 03046, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Conventional gas turbine is reaching its saturation level and further improvement in the cycle efficiency is possible through redesigning the cycle. One of the effective methods is to introduce a Pressure Gain Combustor (PGC) in place of the conventional deflagration combustor as PGC contributes to a considerable gain in thermal efficiency. Pulsed Detonation Combustor (PDC) and Rotating Detonation Combustor (RDC) are the two most prevalent combustor designs for pressure gain combustion. The major challenges of integrating PGCs to existing conventional cycles are the highly unsteady exhaust flow from PGC, high exhaust temperatures from PGC, potential back flow from combustor to compressor. As turbines are designed for much steadier flows, this unsteady exhaust flow and high temperature exhaust gas from PGC is challenging for the turbine of the cycle and its design. One of the solutions is to have an ejector between the PGC and turbine in order to reduce the flow fluctuations, flow velocity and flow temperature. In this work, different cycle layouts of Turbojet and Turbofan engines working with RDC are described. Low order RDC and ejector models are used in this paper. As the ejector is being used, the compressed air from the compressor is split for RDC, ejector, turbine blade cooling. The different cases for the compressed air split are also examined. The performance parameters of the engines are evaluated for different compressor pressure ratios, fan pressure ratios, bypass ratios. Finally, an exergy analysis is performed on all components.

1. Introduction

As global warming and pollution emissions are major concerns in today's world, several studies and research are being carried out to reduce emissions. The transportation system is a major source of pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. Meanwhile, the usage of air transportation is growing on a yearly basis. International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) [1] predicts an increase by 2.2 times in the next twenty years, implying a significant increase in CO₂ emissions from air transport [2]. Researchers in US have conducted a study on intercity air travel [3] and found out that the associated CO₂ emissions averaged 128.4 million tons annually. Estimated annular CH₄ and NO emissions were approximately 5.3 million tons and 1.06 million tons respectively. Thus, reduction of emissions from air transportation is vital in limiting the effects of climate change. Gas turbine engines are already approaching the efficiency limit imposed by the underlying Joule cycle. A promising way to go beyond this limitation is to use a redesigned engine. One of the approaches to this redesign is to switch from deflagration combustion to detonation combustion, where the combustion process happens in the supersonic regime and generates

a rise in total pressure of up to 30% during the combustion process. This process is known as Pressure Gain Combustion (PGC). Studies have shown that PGC can yield a considerable gain in thermal efficiency. The most popular approaches for achieving PGC are Pulsed Detonation Combustion (PDC) and Rotating Detonation Combustion (RDC). In RDC, the combustion mixture is injected axially and the ignition is self-sustained by a detonation wave rotating around the annulus. RDC yields much steadier flow, fewer initiation losses and low NO_x emission [4] compared to PDC. These attributes, as well as high power density, have made RDC the more attractive option for thrust generation and gas turbine engine interaction. Several authors have conducted experimental and numerical research to study detonation combustion processes. Among the numerical studies, Schwer [5,6] designed 3D RDC and investigated several aspects of hydrogen-air RDC including pressure effects, combustor size and different inlet effects on performance. Sousa [7] modelled RDC using 2D method of characteristics followed by a supersonic turbine and studied the overall thermodynamic cycle analysis. On the experimental side, researchers at TU Berlin have investigated different aspects of RDC experimentally including rotating wave

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: gokkul.raj.varatharajulu.purgunan@tu-berlin.de (G.R. Varatharajulu Purgunan), panagiotis.stathopoulos@dlr.de (P. Stathopoulos).

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Nomenclature

<i>A</i>	Area
<i>B</i>	Bypass ratio
<i>Bi</i>	Biot number
<i>c_p</i>	Specific heat at constant pressure
<i>c_{fw}</i>	Wall friction co-efficient
<i>Ex</i>	Exergy
<i>ex</i>	Specific Exergy
<i>h</i>	Enthalpy
<i>IP</i>	Improvement Potential
<i>M</i>	Mach number
<i>n</i>	Number of moles
<i>P</i>	Pressure
<i>q</i>	Heat release
<i>R</i>	Gas constant
<i>s</i>	Entropy
<i>St</i>	Stanton number
<i>T</i>	Temperature
<i>V</i>	Velocity
<i>z</i>	Altitude

Abbreviation

<i>BPR</i>	Bypass Ratio
<i>CPR</i>	Compressor Pressure Ratio
<i>FPR</i>	Fan Pressure Ratio
<i>LHV</i>	Lower Heating Value
<i>PDC</i>	Pulsed Detonation Combustor
<i>PGC</i>	Pressure Gain Combustor
<i>RDC</i>	Rotating Detonation Combustor
<i>SFC</i>	Specific Fuel Consumption
<i>SS</i>	Single Spool configuration
<i>TS</i>	Two Spool configuration

Greek Symbols

α	Mass flow fraction of RDC
χ	Relative exergy destruction
δ	Fuel depletion rate
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate
ϵ	Cooling effectiveness
η	Efficiency
γ	Specific heat ratio
λ	Productivity lack
μ	Mass flow fraction of ejector
π	Pressure ratio
ρ	Density
ϵ	Exergy efficiency
ξ	Mass flow fraction of turbine blade cooling

Greek Symbols

<i>a</i>	Air
<i>act</i>	Actual

<i>b</i>	Combustion
<i>bl</i>	Blade
<i>c</i>	Compressor
<i>ch</i>	Chemical
<i>CJ</i>	Chapman–Jouguet
<i>cl</i>	Cooling air
<i>cn</i>	Cold nozzle
<i>cr</i>	Critical
<i>d</i>	Destruction
<i>det</i>	Detonation
<i>e</i>	Exit
<i>ej</i>	Ejector
<i>ex</i>	Exergy
<i>f</i>	Fuel
<i>fa</i>	Fan
<i>ge</i>	Gas at exit
<i>gi</i>	Gas at inlet
<i>hn</i>	Hot nozzle
<i>i</i>	Inlet
<i>inj</i>	Injection
<i>ite</i>	Intake
<i>m</i>	Mechanical Transmission
<i>n</i>	Nozzle
<i>ob</i>	Oblique shock
<i>p</i>	Product
<i>ph</i>	Physical
<i>pl</i>	Plenum
<i>ref</i>	Reference
<i>s</i>	Static quantities
<i>sl</i>	Sea level
<i>t</i>	Total quantities
<i>tbc</i>	Turbine blade cooling
<i>tf</i>	Turbofan
<i>th</i>	Thermal
<i>theo</i>	Theoretical
<i>tj</i>	Turbojet
<i>tu</i>	Turbine

transition [8], reactant mixing characteristics [9], and investigating the effect of outlet restriction on operating mode of the RDC [10].

Researches have also examined the RDC with compressor, turbine, entire engine with experimental and also numerical approaches. Wolanski [11] conducted an experimental study of RDC in GTD-350 engine and showed that the specific fuel consumption is lower than nominal

and the RDC with gas turbine engine can result in increased cycle efficiency. Naples [12] replaced the conventional combustor with RDC in an existing T63 gas turbine engine and ran several tests for around 20mins. They concluded that the turbine inlet unsteadiness of RDC is far higher when compared with conventional combustors and also the high frequency disturbance of RDC are dissipated rapidly in the turbine. Higashi [13] did an experimental study of disc shaped RDC integrated with centrifugal compressor and a radial flow turbine. They concluded that the angle of the exhaust gas angle is greatly different from the design value which resulted in a large flow separation in the turbine. Zhou [14] experimentally integrated the RDC with an axial turbine to investigate the detonation wave. They have also attached a guide vane before the exhaust gas reaches the turbine to reduce the inlet flow angle for the turbine. On the numerical approach, Ji [15] have conducted a performance analysis of multi-annular RDC with aero-turbine engines and compared with conventional gas turbine engine. They concluded that at the RDC aero engines has higher performance for lower compressor pressure ratio. Liu [16] numerically investigated about the integration of RDC with supersonic turbines. They modelled a nozzle in between the RDC and the supersonic turbine in order to dampen the flow fluctuations from RDC. They showed that the leading-edge shock waves were the main reasons for the overall loss

mechanism. Stathopoulos [17] discussed various cycle layouts for PGC integration to gas turbine engine. He suggested to have an additional secondary compressor for the turbine blade cooling due to increase in total pressure across the combustor and also showed an increase in performance.

The main limitations in integrating the RDC with gas turbine engines are the highly unsteady exhaust flow from PGC, high exhaust temperatures, potential back flow from combustor to compressor. The back flow from RDC to compressor could cause unfavourable effects on the compressor operability and engine stability. In order to reduce the back flow, either a compressor plenum or an isolator with wedges can be utilized as shown in [15]. To dampen the flow fluctuations from RDC, an ejector can be used in between the RDC and turbine. Ejector is practically a sophisticated mixing element, in which the compressed air from the compressor is mixed with the exhaust of the RDC to reduce the flow fluctuations before it enters the turbine. This method was used experimentally by Naples [18] in which they used ejector at the exhaust of RDC for the reduction of turbine inlet temperature and pressure fluctuations and provided conclusive results that RDC can be integrated to turbine. Another approach is to optimize the design of the turbine for the unsteady pulsating flows. Fernelius [19] conducted optimization of turbine geometry for pulsing flow in order to overcome the losses in turbine and to make the integration of PGC into gas turbine engine more beneficial. Their optimized model results demonstrated decrease in entropy generation, flow fluctuation in the blade passage and flow separation. Asli [20] optimized a two-stage axial turbine using kriging model and complex shape method. They optimized the solidity ratio and blade outlet angle of the first stage with entropy generation as the objective function. Their optimized results showed a reduction of 16% in entropy generation and 14.2% gain in the overall turbine power.

In the current work, a lower order cycle analysis of turbojet and turbofan engines working with RDC is studied. A 0-D approach for the RDC for calculating the exit total pressure and exit total temperature is described [21]. Various types of ejectors which can be used in between the RDC and turbine are explained in detail and the results are shown. Different cycle layouts such as turbojet, single spool turbofan and two spool turbofan are examined. The compressor air split between the RDC, ejector and turbine blade cooling are done for different cases and evaluated. The performance metrics are calculated by varying compressor pressure ratio, fan pressure ratio and bypass ratio for different layouts. The result shows that the turbofan with single spool showed better performance than other two layouts. Also, in this paper, by integrating an ejector, there is a loss in total pressure and turbine inlet total pressure is lower than the primary compressor outlet pressure. Thus an ejector is beneficial not only for the reduction in flow fluctuation, flow velocity but also for eliminating the use of secondary compressor. Finally, exergy analysis were performed.

2. Methodology

The different layouts with station numbering are shown in Fig. 1. All the components are modelled using a 0-D approach. The thermodynamic models are explained in the following sections. The ideal thermodynamic cycles are shown in Fig. 2. In Fig. 2, the air enters at 0, the air is then compressed and decelerated by the compressor 0-3; for the detonation cycle, there is an increase in pressure across the combustor at 35 while for Joule cycle there is a constant pressure; for the detonation cycle, the ejector is used to dampen the flow fluctuations, to reduce the flow temperature and velocity where there is also loss in total pressure at turbine inlet 4; then the mixture is expanded through the turbine and nozzle 8. When compared with conventional aero engines, the detonation engine is advantageous. (1) There is an increase in thermal efficiency with a low entropy generation, (2) The combustors are compact and also from literatures, the detonation combustors are more efficient at low compressor pressure ratio. Therefore, less stages

of compressors and turbines are required, which further reduces the size of the engine.

Few assumptions were made for the cycle analysis,

- All process are assumed to be steady state.
- The fuel used in RDC is hydrogen.
- Constant isentropic efficiency for compression and expansion process.
- The air and combustion product are treated as an ideal gas.

2.1. Intake

For the intake, the atmospheric conditions at different altitudes are calculated using International Standard Atmosphere (ISA) correlations [22] as shown in Eqs. (1) and (2) in which z is altitude in m . P_{sl} and T_{sl} are the pressure and temperature in sea-level which are 101325 Pa and 288.15 K.

$$P_0(z) = P_{sl} \left(1 - 0.0065 \frac{z}{T_0} \right)^{5.2561} \quad (1)$$

$$T_0(z) = T_{sl} - 6.5 \frac{z}{1000} \quad (2)$$

The intake pressure and temperatures are found using,

$$P_{t1} = P_0 \left(1 + \eta_{ite} \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_0^2 \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (3)$$

$$T_{t1} = T_0 \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_0^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

2.2. Fan

For the modelling of fan, the fan pressure ratio, bypass ratio and isentropic efficiencies are specified.

$$P_{t2} = P_{t1} \pi_{fa} \quad (5)$$

$$T_{t2} = T_{t1} (\pi_{fa})^{\frac{\gamma - 1}{\eta_c}} \quad (6)$$

With the bypass ratio, the mass flow rate for the primary and secondary duct can be calculated.

$$\dot{m}_{cn} = \frac{\dot{m}_a B}{B + 1} \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{m}_{hn} = \frac{\dot{m}_a}{B + 1}$$

2.3. Compressor

The outlet total pressure and total temperature are obtained using the compressor pressure ratio and isentropic efficiency of the compressor. For turbojet, $\pi_{fa} = 1$ as there is no fan component.

$$P_{t3} = P_{t1} \pi_{fa} \pi_c \quad (8)$$

$$T_{t3} = T_{t1} (\pi_{fa})^{\frac{\gamma - 1}{\eta_c}} \left[1 + \frac{(\pi_c)^{\frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma}}}{\eta_c} \right] \quad (9)$$

As we have the RDC downstream of the compressor, there is a possibility of potential back flow of the shock wave which could have negative effects on the compressor stability. In order to overcome this, a compressor plenum can be used. With the view to the size and weight of the engine, this plenum should be as small as possible. Neumann [23] modelled a plenum between the NASA E^3 compressor and the PDC tubes to reduce the risk of back flow. They concluded that having the compressor plenum is beneficial when using PGC downstream to the compressor. A simplified 0D plenum is assumed at compressor exit where the axial velocity is zero and a fixed static temperature is considered similar to [23].

Fig. 1. Different Cycle Layouts.

Fig. 2. Ideal thermodynamic process of Joules cycle and Humphrey cycle. (Black line indicating Joules cycle and Red line indicates Humphrey cycle.). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. RDC Annulus.

2.4. Rotating detonation combustor

In this work, RDC is used as the combustor in place of the conventional constant pressure combustor. The experimental results and numerical simulations have shown the RDC's main flow features, which can be characterized by one or more detonation waves propagating around the annulus, followed by a series of expansion waves, an oblique shock and a slip line, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The thermodynamic process of RDC can be simplified as: injection, detonation combustion and expansion. From Fig. 3(a), the pressure behind the detonation wave θ_{det} decays to the critical pressure θ_{inj} and the fresh mixture begins to refill at the chamber. The injectors are blocked in the expansion region due to the high pressure in the combustion chamber. In this model, the reactants enter the chamber at a constant velocity V_{inj} .

The gas composition in the injection plane is given as a premixed mixture containing hydrogen–air (21% oxygen and 79% nitrogen). As the analysis is done at stoichiometric conditions, the gas composition at the outlet of RDC is water–nitrogen and the minor species are neglected.

For this paper, an in-house 0-D RDC model [21] has been utilized. For calculating the outlet total pressure, either taking mean of the pressure distribution [24] or mass flow average method [15] can be used. In this model, the mass flow averaged outlet pressure is used in Eq. (10).

$$P_{t,35} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} P(\theta) d\theta \quad (10)$$

From Fig. 3(a), we can split the pressure distribution into three regions which is shown in Eq. (11)

$$P_{t,35} = \frac{1}{2\pi x_1} \left(\int_0^{\theta_{inj-1}} P_{inj} d\theta \right) + \frac{P_{CJ} h_{det}}{2\pi \Delta\theta_{expansion}} \left(\int_0^{\sigma} f(\sigma) d\sigma \right) + \frac{1}{2\pi x_2} \left(\int_{\theta_{det+1}}^{2\pi} P_{inj} d\theta \right) \quad (11)$$

where $x_1 = \theta_{inj-1} - 0$ and $x_2 = 2\pi - \theta_{det+1}$

In Eq. (11), the integration of the first and third terms on the right side is P_{inj} as the reactants enter the combustor at a constant velocity and no pressure loss in injector. The second term on the right side has two quantities with length dimensions, namely, h_{det} and $\Delta\theta_{expansion}$. From the experiments of Sichel and Foster [25], the value of the ratio is known to be 2.90. The integration limit for the second term will be from 0 to 2.90. Therefore, for the 0-D approach, the exit pressure can be calculated using Eq. (12).

$$P_{t,35} = P_{inj} + \frac{P_{CJ}}{2\pi \cdot 2.90} \int_0^{2.90} f(\sigma) d\sigma + P_{inj} \quad (12)$$

For the 0-D model, the injection pressure can be formulated as in Eq. (13),

$$P_{inj} = G P_{pl} \left[\frac{\gamma + 1}{2 + (\gamma - 1)} \right]^{1/2} \left(\frac{2}{\gamma + 1} \right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (13)$$

where G is the correction factor which includes the effect of A_{cr}/A_{inj} and M_{inj} , so that the pressure gain is not overestimated. The value of G can taken as less than 1. The plenum pressure P_{pl} can be taken as the compressor outlet pressure as there will be no total pressure loss inside the plenum.

The exit total temperature can be calculated iteratively using the total enthalpy at the exit and the entropy at the exit.

$$h_{t,35} = h_{t,3} + q \quad (14)$$

where, the heat release q is computed as shown in Eq. (15) where n is the number of moles, Δh_f is the formation enthalpy and η_b is the combustion efficiency,

$$q = \eta_b \Delta h_{f,p} n_p \quad (15)$$

The exit entropy can be calculated using Eq. (16). The entropy generation due to the detonation front and due to oblique shock can be calculated using the Shock and Detonation tool box [26].

$$s_{35} = s_3 + c_{p,35} \ln \left[\frac{T_{t,35}}{T_{t,3}} \right] - R_{35} \ln \left[\frac{P_{t,35}}{P_{t,3}} \right] = s_{CJ} + s_{ob} \quad (16)$$

A fixed static pressure at the outlet can be considered and then the exit mach number, exit static temperature and exit velocity can be calculated using the isentropic relations.

Fig. 4 shows the variation of pressure gain as a function of plenum temperature and equivalence ratio. As the plenum temperature is increased, the pressure gain drops. This is due to the fact that, the detonation wave becomes less intense with increasing temperature, that is, the higher the inlet temperature, the lower the detonation parameters such as M_{CJ} and P_{CJ} . For higher equivalence ratio, the intensity of the detonation wave is higher, which increases the pressure gain.

2.5. Ejector

In this section, three different types of ejectors are shown. The ejector modelling and calculations are similar to that of [27,28] with a few modifications.

For ejector 1, as shown in Fig. 5(a), the primary flow from RDC and the secondary flow from the compressor is at a constant static

Fig. 4. Pressure gain as a function of plenum temperature and equivalence ratio.

pressure. The mixing of the two streams happens at the state 36. The total temperature, velocity and Mach number at 36 is calculated using the conservation equation,

$$\dot{m}_{31}c_{p31}T_{i31} + \dot{m}_{35}c_{p35}T_{i35} = \dot{m}_{36}c_{p36}T_{i36} \quad (17)$$

$$\dot{m}_{31}V_{31} + \dot{m}_{35}V_{35} = \dot{m}_{36}V_{36} \quad (18)$$

$$V_{36} = M_{36} \sqrt{\gamma_{36} R_{36} T_{i36} \frac{T_{36}}{T_{i36}}} \quad (19)$$

The temperature ratio of T_{36}/T_{i36} is a function of M_{36} .

At state 36, the parameters such as c_p , R , γ are obtained using the correlations [27,28] between the primary and secondary flow.

$$c_{p36} = c_{p35} \left[\frac{1 + \mu \frac{c_{p31}}{c_{p35}}}{1 + \mu} \right] \quad R_{36} = \left[\frac{R_{35} + \mu R_{31}}{1 + \mu} \right] \quad \gamma_{36} = \left[\frac{\gamma_{35} + \mu \gamma_{31}}{1 + \mu} \right] \quad (20)$$

where $\mu = \frac{\dot{m}_{31}}{\dot{m}_{35}}$.

From 36 to 37, constant area diffuser is used. For a supersonic flow, with a constant area section, the Mach number is reduced due to shock formation but there is an increase in static pressure and temperature. The static pressure rise at 37 is calculated using,

$$\frac{P_{s37}}{P_{s36}} = r_d \left(\frac{2}{\gamma_{36} + 1} M_{36}^2 - \frac{\gamma_{36} - 1}{\gamma_{36} + 1} \right) \quad (21)$$

where r_d is an empirical pressure rise co-efficient and the value can be taken less than 1.25 according to [27]. The Mach number at 37 can be calculated as a function of static pressure and impulse function.

$$P_{s37} = \left(\frac{F_{37}}{A_{37}(\gamma_{36} + 1)M_{37}^2} \right) \quad (22)$$

where F_{37} is the impulse function which is given as,

$$F_{37} = P_{36}A_{36}(1 + \gamma_{36}M_{36}^2) - \pi D_{37}L_{37}c_{fw}P_{36} \frac{\gamma_{36}}{2} M_{36}^2.$$

As the section is a constant area section, the increase in static temperature across the section can be found using,

$$\frac{T_{37}}{T_{36}} = \frac{(T/T^*)_{M_{37}}}{(T/T^*)_{M_{36}}} \quad (23)$$

A diverging diffuser further reduces the flow velocity between state 37 and 4. The Mach number at 4 can be calculated using the Area-Mach number relation. The diverging diffuser efficiency will be lower as there will be a formation of thick boundary layer. From [28], the diffuser efficiency can be taken as 60%. Across the diffuser, the total temperature is constant and the total pressure is calculated using isentropic relations.

Table 1
Flow parameters used for Fig. 6.

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
M_{31}	0.25	T_{31} (K)	400
M_{35}	Varying	T_{35} (K)	2300
P_{35} (bar)	12.15	μ	0.5

$$\frac{P_{s4}}{P_{s37}} = \left[1 + 0.6 \left(\frac{P_{i37}}{P_{s37}} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{T_{s4}}{T_{s37}} = \left[1 + 0.6 \left(\left[\frac{T_{i37}}{T_{s37}} \right]^{\frac{\gamma_{36}-1}{\gamma_{36}}} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (25)$$

The ejector 2 as shown in Fig. 5(b) is similar ejector 1 but without the constant area diffuser. If the flow from RDC is at low supersonic speed ($M_{35} < 1.3$), then when the primary flow mixes with secondary flow, the flow becomes subsonic ($M_{36} \approx 0.9$). If there is a constant area duct with a subsonic flow at the inlet, the flow velocity increases and also with diverging duct at the exit of constant area duct will further increase the flow velocity which is not ideal for this case. Thus for a low supersonic flow from RDC, the ejector 2 can be used instead of ejector 1.

For the ejector 3 configuration, the primary flow and secondary flow enter at different static pressure ($P_{s31} < P_{s35}$). For this model, it is assumed that the streams do not mix between the state 35 and 36. Also, the flow is isentropic between 35 and 36. The total temperature at 36 can be calculated using Eq. (17). The Mach number at 37 can be obtained using the relations from [27]. Once M_{37} is calculated, the static pressure at 37 can be found with the impulse function. For this ejector model, both streams enter at different static pressure, therefore the impulse function can be written as, $F_{37} = P_{s31}A_{31}(1 + \gamma_{31}M_{31}^2) + P_{s35}A_{35}(1 + \gamma_{35}M_{35}^2) - \pi D_{37}L_{37}c_{fw}P_{35} \frac{\gamma_{36}}{2} M_{36}^2$. At state 4, for divergent diffuser, the flow parameters can be calculated similarly to that of ejector 1.

The Fig. 6 shows the total pressure, static pressure, total temperature, static temperature and Mach number across the ejector for the three configurations as in Fig. 5.

2.6. Turbine

For the turbojet configuration, the turbine shaft is coupled with the compressor. For the turbofan single spool configuration, the turbine shaft is coupled with compressor and fan. Finally, for the turbofan two spool configuration, the turbine ($T1$) shaft is coupled with compressor ($C1$) and the turbine ($T2$) shaft is coupled with the fan. Based on the configuration, the work balance is determined.

For turbojet configuration,

$$T_{i5,tj} = T_{i4} - \frac{c_{p3}(T_{i3} - T_{i2})}{c_{p4}\eta_m} \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{P_{i5}}{P_{i4}} = \left(\frac{T_{i5}}{T_{i4}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma_4}{\gamma_4-1}} \quad (27)$$

For single spool turbofan configuration,

$$T_{i5,ss} = T_{i4} - \frac{c_{p3}(T_{i3} - T_{i2})}{c_{p4}\eta_m} - (B+1) \frac{c_{pa}(T_{i2} - T_{i1})}{c_{p4}\eta_m} \quad (28)$$

For two spool turbofan configuration,

$$T_{i5,ts} = T_{i4} - \frac{c_{p3}(T_{i3} - T_{i2})}{c_{p4}\eta_m} \quad (29)$$

$$T_{i6} = T_{i5,ts} - (B+1) \frac{c_{pa}(T_{i2} - T_{i1})}{c_{p4}\eta_m} \quad (30)$$

As the inlet temperature of the turbine is high, turbine blade cooling becomes essential. Film cooling is one of the most popular methods for the cooling of turbine blades. With the coolant mass flow rate known,

Fig. 5. Different Ejectors.

Fig. 6. Ejector flow parameters variation.

Fig. 7. Total pressure and total temperature variation along the TurboJet engine.

the total temperature can be calculated using the energy conservation equation. The detailed explanation of turbine blade cooling is given in Appendix A.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{m}_4 H_4 + \dot{m}_{32} H_{32} &= \dot{m}_5 H_5 = (\dot{m}_4 + \dot{m}_{32}) H_5 \\ \dot{m}_4 c_{p,4} T_{t,4} + \dot{m}_{32} c_{p,32} T_{t,32} &= (\dot{m}_4 + \dot{m}_{32}) c_{p,5} T_{t,5} \\ c_{p,4} T_{t,4} + \xi c_{p,32} T_{t,32} &= (1 + \xi) c_{p,5} T_{t,5} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

where $\xi = \frac{\dot{m}_{32}}{\dot{m}_4}$.

Similarly, blade cooling can be done for turbine (T2).

2.7. Hot and cold nozzle

The hot and cold nozzle in the turbojet and turbofan cases is calculated in a similar way depending on whether the nozzle is choked or not. The nozzle pressure ratio $\pi_n = \frac{P_7}{P_0}$ and critical pressure ratio $\pi_{cr} = \frac{P_7}{P_{cr}}$ determines the choking condition. If $\pi_n > \pi_{cr}$, the nozzle is choked and if $\pi_n < \pi_{cr}$, the nozzle is unchoked.

$$P_{cr} = P_7 \left[1 - \frac{\gamma - 1}{\eta_n(\gamma + 1)} \right]^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma - 1}} \quad (32)$$

2.8. Performance parameters

The parameters such as specific thrust, specific fuel consumption, fuel-air ratio and thermal efficiency are calculated.

The specific thrust for turbojet is as follows,

$$F_{s,tj} = (V_8 - V_0) + \left(\frac{P_8 - P_0}{\rho_8 V_8} \right) \quad (33)$$

For turbofan, we have two thrust from cold and hot nozzle.

$$\begin{aligned} F_{cn} &= (V_{25} - V_0) + \left(\frac{P_{25} - P_0}{\rho_{25} V_{25}} \right) \\ F_{hn} &= (V_8 - V_0) + \left(\frac{P_8 - P_0}{\rho_8 V_8} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

For overall air mass flow rate \dot{m}_a , the specific thrust is given by,

$$F_{s,tj} = \frac{F_{cn} B}{B + 1} + \frac{F_{hn}}{B + 1} \quad (35)$$

The fuel-air ratio can be obtained using the following equation,

$$\begin{aligned} (1 + f_{theo}) c_{p35} (T_{t35} - T_{ref}) + f_{theo} \Delta H_{35} + c_{p3} (T_{ref} - T_{t3}) &= 0 \\ \eta_b = \frac{f_{theo}}{f_{act}} \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

The specific fuel consumption is found as a function of mass flow rate of fuel and thrust,

$$SFC = \frac{\dot{m}_f 3600}{F_s} \quad (37)$$

Table 2

Constant parameters used for the calculations.

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
η_{hc}	0.93	η_{fa}	0.90
η_c	0.87	η_b	0.98
η_{tu}	0.9	η_m	0.99
η_n	0.95	π_c	Varying

The thermal efficiency can be calculated by [29],

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{\left((1 + f_{act}) \frac{V_8^2}{2} - \frac{V_0^2}{2} \right) + \left(\frac{(1 + f_{act}) P_8^2 - P_0^2}{\rho_8^2 V_8^2} \right)}{f_{act} LHV} \quad (38)$$

As not all mass flow enters the RDC, the RDC air split parameter, $\alpha = \frac{\dot{m}_{rdc}}{\dot{m}_a}$ should be considered for the above equations.

3. Results and discussion

Table 2 shows the efficiency of different components used for this work and the constant values are taken from [17].

3.1. Performance and cycle results of the TurboJet configuration

3.1.1. Pressure and temperature variation within the cycle

Fig. 7 shows the total pressure and temperature along the cycle. It shows a similar trend and good agreement with the thermodynamic process as shown in Fig. 2.

3.1.2. Performance analysis of TurboJet

The performance metrics of the turbojet configuration for different altitudes and with varying compressor pressure ratio are shown in the Fig. 8. For the calculations, neither the combustor outlet temperature nor turbine inlet temperature were limited. From Fig. 8(a), it is clear that specific thrust increases with respect to the compressor pressure ratio. For lower compressor pressure ratios, a steep increase in specific thrust is observed, whereas for high compressor pressure ratios, the change in specific thrust as a function of CPR is minimal. A possible reason for this is the reduction of pressure gain in the RDC with increasing inlet plenum temperature. For higher compressor pressure ratio, the compressor outlet temperature increases, which could reduce the pressure gain but there is also a slight increase in combustor outlet temperature. The fuel-air ratio remains almost constant for different CPR and different altitudes. The specific fuel consumption drops with compressor pressure ratio, as it is inversely proportional to the specific thrust. For low CPR, the thermal efficiency is lower as T_8 is lower and this is the main factor influencing the thermal efficiency and the thermal efficiency increases with increase in CPR. It is interesting to see from Fig. 8(d) that, the thermal efficiency for compressor ratio ($\pi_c > 10$) is low at higher altitude when compared with lower altitude. For low π_c , the exit pressure P_8 is low, so does ρ_8 and f_{act} . This reduction in ρ_8 and f_{act} overcomes the low P_8 and increases the thermal efficiency for higher altitudes. But for high π_c , the exit pressure is higher than the low CPR, so does the f_{act} . The increase in f_{act} is a factor for reduction in thermal efficiency with increasing altitudes.

3.1.3. Influence of compressor flow rate split on TurboJet performance

The compressed air is split into three stream - (1) for RDC, (2) for ejector, (3) for turbine blade cooling (see Fig. 1(a)). The mass flow rate fraction is varied for each component as shown in Table 3. where, $\dot{m}_a = \dot{m}_{rdc} + \dot{m}_{eje} + \dot{m}_{tbc}$, $\alpha = \frac{\dot{m}_{rdc}}{\dot{m}_a}$, $\mu = \frac{\dot{m}_{eje}}{\dot{m}_{rdc}}$ and $\xi = \frac{\dot{m}_{tbc}}{\dot{m}_{rdc} + \dot{m}_{eje}}$.

Here, the total mass flow rate is not specified and the mass flow fraction is used with respect to \dot{m}_a . The total temperature variation across the turbojet engine is shown in Fig. 9. From the intake to the combustor, there is no change in total temperature and the total temperature is different for different cases from state 35 downstream.

Fig. 8. Performance parameters of TurboJet from sea level to 11 km above sea level for $M_0 = 0$.

Fig. 9. Total temperature variation along the TurboJet engine for the 5 cases from Table 3.

Table 3
Compressed air split for various components.
The various \dot{m} are with respect to the \dot{m}_a .

Case	\dot{m}_{rdc} (%)	\dot{m}_{ejc} (%)	\dot{m}_{tbc} (%)
1	50	25	15
2	55	25	15
3	50	25	20
4	50	30	15
5	50	20	20

At state 4, the ejector outlet, the total temperature depends on the ejector mass flow fraction μ . Case 4 has the highest value for μ , while case 5 has the lowest value for μ . As a result, the total temperature for case 4 is low and for case 5 is high. Similarly, the total temperature across the turbine also depends on the mass flow fraction of turbine blade cooling parameter ξ . The performance parameters are plotted in the Fig. 10. The high specific thrust is for case 2, as the nozzle exit temperature and pressure were high, which also increases the thermal efficiency. The exit temperature is lowest for case 4, leading also to a lower thermal efficiency and lower specific thrust. For case 2,

even though the specific thrust and thermal efficiency are high, so is the turbine inlet temperature. For a practical application, the turbine inlet temperature is limited to the turbine blade material. As a result, the deciding criteria for the compressor split should include not only performance parameters, but also flow parameters.

3.2. Analysis of TurboFan configuration

3.2.1. Variation of pressure and temperature in TurboFan

The Fig. 11 shows the total pressure and temperature along the single spool and two spool turbofan cycle. The figure shows the similar trend and good agreement with the thermodynamic cycle as in Fig. 2.

3.2.2. Sensitivity evaluation of TurboFan

In this section, the sensitivity analyses of layout 2 and layout 3 are carried out by varying the fan pressure ratio and by-pass pressure ratio. The specific thrust and SFC are calculated by varying the fan pressure ratio and the bypass ratio. For the increase in fan pressure ratio, we could see that it has positive effect on the specific thrust and SFC. This is due to the fact for higher fan pressure ratio, the pressure at the exit of cold nozzle is higher. With $B > 1$, the cold nozzle is has more effect on performance compared with hot nozzle. As a result, specific thrust is higher and SFC is lower. Increasing bypass ratio improves the SFC but there is a significant reduction in the specific thrust. These analyses and trends are similar to that of [30].

3.2.3. Performance metrics of TurboFan

The results on the performance metrics for turbofan SS configuration for different altitudes with $B = 5$, $\pi_f = 1.6$ are shown in Fig. 13. The specific thrust shows that the higher the altitude the lower the thrust. This is due to the fact that, with by-pass ratio greater than one, the cold nozzle thrust becomes the dominant factor than the hot nozzle as in Eq. (35). With increasing altitude, the pressure and temperature drop, which reduces the exit velocity V_{25} and the specific thrust. The specific thrust is with respect to the total air mass flow rate and the total air mass flow rate is higher for the turbofan than the turbojet which results in higher specific thrust. The fuel-air ratio is almost constant over the different pressure ratios similar to that of turbojet

Fig. 10. Variation of performance parameters for cases from Table 3.

Fig. 11. Pressure and Temperature variation of Layout 2 and Layout 3.

configuration. The SFC drops with increasing specific thrust. A decline in thermal efficiency can be observed as the compressor pressure is increased. This is because, with the increase in CPR, there is a reduction in total temperature at the turbine outlet. In the Eq. (28), with increase in compressor pressure ratio, on the right side, the second term increases largely, while third term decreases slightly due to increase in c_{p4} . Thus the outlet temperature T_8 and the outlet velocity V_8 decreases with increase in CPR. Therefore the thermal efficiency declines. This reduction in V_8 does not affect the specific thrust because, as mentioned before, for $B > 1$ the cold nozzle is dominant factor than the hot nozzle.

The performance metrics for turbofan TS configuration are done for different altitudes with $B = 5$, $\pi_f = 1.6$ are shown in Fig. 14. The specific thrust, fuel-air ratio and SFC variation is similar to that of SS configuration. The specific thrust is lower for two spool configuration when comparing with single spool configuration and this is

because of the additional turbine which reduces the exit pressure and temperature. For the two spool configuration, the thermal efficiency increases with increase in CPR unlike single spool configuration as shown in Fig. 14(d). The term T_{15} decreases and T_{16} increases slightly with increase in CPR. Thus the exit temperature T_8 and exit velocity V_8 increases slightly due to increase in c_{p4} with respect to CPR. For both the turbofan configurations, the change in thermal efficiency is lower with respect to CPR and altitude.

3.3. Exergy analysis

Exergy can be defined as the maximum available work that can be produced by an energy system as it comes to equilibrium with its reference environment. Exergy analysis combines both first law and

Fig. 12. Sensitivity analysis of TurboFan configuration under sea-level condition.

Fig. 13. Performance metric of TurboFan SS from sea level to 11 km above sea level for $M_0 = 0$.

second law of thermodynamics. It provides information on component losses and destruction. The exergy can be divided into four components such as physical, chemical, kinetic and potential exergy.

Few assumptions were considered for this analysis, (1) the turbofan is modelled at the cruise flight phase, that is, at constant flight speed and at constant altitude. Thus, the kinetic and potential exergy were not considered for this study. (2) Chemical exergy is neglected for all components except combustor. (3) The cooling air flow is neglected

since it has negligible effect on exergy analysis [31].

$$\begin{aligned} Ex_t &= Ex_{ph} + Ex_{ch} \\ Ex_t &= \dot{m}(ex_{ph} + ex_{ch}) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

The general exergy balance can be written as follows:

$$\sum Ex_{in} - \sum Ex_{out} = \sum Ex_d \quad (40)$$

Fig. 14. Performance metric of TurboFan TS from sea level to 11 km above sea level for $M_0 = 0$.

Fig. 15. Exergy Analysis in TurboFan single spool configuration.

The specific exergy is calculated as follows:

$$ex = (h - h_{ref}) - T_{ref}(s - s_{ref}) \quad (41)$$

The exergy balance for different components are as follows from Fig. 15:

• Fan

$$\begin{aligned} W_{fa} + Ex_1 - Ex_{25} - Ex_2 - Ex_{d,fa} &= 0 \\ Ex_{d,fa} &= W_{fa} + Ex_1 - Ex_{25} - Ex_2 \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

• Compressor

$$\begin{aligned} W_c + Ex_2 - Ex_3 - Ex_{d,c} &= 0 \\ Ex_{d,c} &= W_c + Ex_2 - Ex_3 \\ Ex_{d,c} &= W_c - \dot{m}_2(ex_3 - ex_2) \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

where,

$$\dot{m}_2(ex_3 - ex_2) = \dot{m}_2 \left\{ c_{p2}(T_{i3} - T_{i2}) - T_{ref} \left[c_{p2} \ln \left(\frac{T_{i3}}{T_{i2}} \right) - R_2 \ln \left(\frac{P_{i3}}{P_{i2}} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (44)$$

• RDC

$$\begin{aligned} Ex_f + Ex_3 - Ex_{35} - Ex_{d,rdc} &= 0 \\ Ex_{d,rdc} &= Ex_f + Ex_3 - Ex_{35} \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where, $Ex_f = \dot{m}_f g_f LHV$. For hydrogen fuel, the fuel exergy factor, $g_f = 0.985$ [31].

• Ejector

$$\begin{aligned} Ex_{35} + Ex_{31} - Ex_4 - Ex_{d,ej} &= 0 \\ Ex_{d,ej} &= Ex_{35} + Ex_{31} - Ex_4 \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

Table 4
Parameters used for exergy analysis.

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
z (m)	11 000	\dot{m}_a (kg/s)	150
T_{ref} (K)	216.15	P_{ref} (bar)	0.274
η_m	0.97	π_{fa}	1.55
B	5	π_c	10

Table 5
Exergy values of TurboFan SS.

Components	Inlet Exergy (MW)	Outlet Exergy (MW)	Destruction Exergy (MW)	Exergy Efficiency (%)
FAN	5.195	4.430	0.765	85.275
C1	7.546	6.646	0.899	88.083
RDC	89.345	72.926	16.419	81.622
EJE	74.708	71.871	2.836	96.202
T1	21.442	20.039	1.403	92.996

- Turbine

$$-W_{tu} + Ex_4 - Ex_5 - Ex_{d,tu} = 0 \quad (47)$$

$$Ex_{d,tu} = -W_{tu} + \dot{m}_4(ex_4 - ex_5)$$

$$\text{where } \dot{m}_4 = \dot{m}_3 + \dot{m}_f.$$

The performance parameters in exergy analysis are given below. For the performance parameters, the exergy used are product and fuel exergy. The product exergy is the output produced and the fuel exergy is the resources used to generate the product.

- Exergy efficiency

$$\varepsilon = \frac{Ex_p}{Ex_f} \quad (48)$$

- Improvement Potential

$$IP = Ex_d(1 - \varepsilon) \quad (49)$$

- Relative exergy destruction

$$\chi = \frac{Ex_d}{\sum Ex_d} \quad (50)$$

- Fuel depletion rate

$$\delta = \frac{Ex_d}{\sum Ex_f} \quad (51)$$

- Productivity lack

$$\lambda = \frac{Ex_d}{\sum Ex_p} \quad (52)$$

The exergy analysis are shown in Table 5 and in Fig. 16. The minimum exergy rate is for the fan because the fan inlet condition is equal to the reference environment condition. The maximum exergy rate is the combustor as it is operated with high energy parameter (fuel). The ejector has the highest exergy efficiency than other component while RDC has the lowest exergy efficiency. The exergy efficiency of RDC is higher than the conventional combustor by around 4%–6%.

The overall exergy efficiency is calculated for the turbofan single spool configuration. The thermal efficiency and exergy efficiency are linearly proportional to each other [32] and this equation can be used for any gas turbine engines which produce shaft power output.

$$\eta_{ex} = \frac{\eta_{th}}{g_f} \quad (53)$$

For hydrogen fuel, the fuel exergy factor, $g_f = 0.985$ [31]. The exergy efficiency for different compressor pressure ratio, fan pressure ratio and bypass ratio is shown in Fig. 17. The exergy efficiency is

higher at lower compressor ratio and at lower bypass ratio. It is beneficial at lower compressor ratio is owing to the fact that low temperatures improves sustainability and reduces fuel depletion [33]. Lower bypass ratios result in higher specific thrust, as illustrated in Fig. 12(c), which leads to higher exergy efficiency.

4. Conclusion

In this work, three different cycle layouts namely, turbojet, turbofan single spool and turbofan two spool configurations working with Rotating Detonation Combustor were evaluated. All the cycle layout are similar with the joule cycle, except with an additional component in between the combustor and turbine. The ejector was used to reduce the flow fluctuation, flow velocity. For the RDC outlet flow parameters, an in-house 0-D model was used. Three different types of ejectors were examined and the flow parameters inside the ejectors were plotted. The work done by the turbine was determined according to the configuration. The outlet flow parameters of the hot and cold nozzle were calculated depending on the nozzle pressure ratio and critical pressure ratio. The performance metric such as specific thrust, fuel-air ratio, specific fuel consumption and thermal efficiency were calculated for varying altitudes and compressor pressure ratio. Finally, an exergy analysis was done for all components and also overall exergy analysis was computed for varying CPR, BPR and FPR. The numbering of different components were specified in Fig. 1.

For the turbojet, pressure–temperature variation, performance parameters at different altitudes, various compressor air split cases were calculated. The variation of the P-T diagram is similar to that of the thermodynamic cycle of a gas turbine engine. For increase in altitude, the specific thrust, SFC shows a positive trend. With the thermal efficiency variation, for higher CPR, it is high at lower altitude than at higher altitude. For the various cases of compressor air split percentage, the case 2 showed the better performance and case 4 showed the lowest performance. Not all compressed air was used in the calculation, only 90%–95% were taken, while the rest of the compressed air can be used for other aircraft components such as pressuring the cabins, etc. The deciding criteria for the compressor split should include not only performance parameters, but also flow parameters due to material limitations. For the turbofan, pressure–temperature variation, sensitivity analysis, performance parameters at different altitudes were determined. The air from the cold nozzle and hot nozzle are mixed at the outlet directly and not before. A sensitivity analysis for turbofan was done by varying the fan pressure ratio and bypass ratio. The plots followed the same trends as the literatures. The specific thrust of turbofan could be seen lower than the turbojet, but it is with respect to the overall air mass flow rate. The intake air mass flow rate is always greater for turbofan and thus the total thrust will be higher for the turbofan than turbojet. By comparing the performance metric, of all three layouts, the turbofan single spool configuration showed better performance in terms of parameters.

Exergy analysis has been done for the turbofan configuration. The exergy destruction for RDC is little higher than the conventional combustor while the exergy efficiency is higher for RDC. The fan is found to have low exergy as the fan inlet condition is equal to the reference condition. The combustor has high exergy as it operated with fuel which has high energy. The performance metric of exergy analysis is calculated and plotted. The combustion chamber is shown to be the most promising component to be improved, with an improvement potential of 3.02 MW. The other components have a relatively low improvement potential. Also, the overall exergy efficiency was calculated for varying compressor pressure ratio, fan pressure ratio and bypass ratio. The overall exergy efficiency is higher at lower compressor pressure ratio and lower bypass ratio.

In real cases there is no result of pressure gain in RDC, the performance metric will not have significant increase. However, the advantage of RDC is not limited to pressure gain; (i) The combustors are

Fig. 16. Exergy Analysis of TurboFan SS.

Fig. 17. Overall Exergy Efficiency of TurboFan SS configuration.

compact, which reduces the overall size of the combustor and engine. (ii) The specific fuel consumption for RDC is lower because hydrogen has a higher heating value than conventional jet fuel, resulting in a lower need of fuel for hydrogen-based engines. (iii) The exergy efficiency is higher for RDC of around 4%–6% when compared with conventional combustor. And, from a cycle standpoint, the improvement should be observed in overall performance measures such as specific thrust, specific fuel consumption, weight and size reductions

rather than component-level performance such as pressure gain across RDC.

Although the standard turbofan single spool layout is advantageous, various other components, such as an afterburner at the turbine outlet, a duct burner in the cold nozzle, and mixing of cold and hot nozzles in a constant area duct before the outlet, can still be incorporated in the cycle. These components could improve thrust and SFC and would be recommended for future work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Gokkul Raj Varatharajulu Purgunan: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Panagiotis Stathopoulos:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Turbine blade cooling

In this section, different types of cooling techniques such as pure convective cooling, pure film cooling, convective cooling combined with film cooling and thermal barrier coating (TBC) and transpiration cooling are discussed. The internal cooling efficiency η_{cl} can be calculated from the internal heat transfer. If the blade material temperature is kept constant, then the cooling efficiency is as follows.

$$\eta_{cl} = \frac{T_{cl,e} - T_{cl,i}}{T_{bl} - T_{cl,i}} = 1 - \exp\left(-St_{cl} \frac{A_{sc}}{A_{ca}}\right) \quad (A.1)$$

where A_{sc} and A_{ca} are the surface and cross-sectional area of the coolant channel inside the blade. The Stanton number is defined as:

$$St_{cl} = \frac{Nu}{RePr} \quad (A.2)$$

With the help of η_{cl} , the temperature difference ratio W^+ can be calculated for different types of cooling as follows.

- Pure convective cooling:

$$W^+ = \frac{\epsilon_o}{\eta_{cl}(1 - \epsilon_o)} \quad (A.3)$$

where the overall cooling effectiveness, ϵ_o , is defined as,

$$\epsilon_o = \frac{T_{gi} - T_{bl}}{T_{gi} - T_{cl,i}} \quad (A.4)$$

- Film cooling [34]:

$$W^+ = \frac{\epsilon_o - \epsilon_{fl}(1 - \eta_{cl}) - \epsilon_o \epsilon_{fl} \eta_{cl}}{\eta_{cl}(1 - \epsilon_o)} \quad (A.5)$$

where the film cooling effectiveness, ϵ_{fl} is defined as,

$$\epsilon_{fl} = \frac{T_{gi} - T_{aw}}{T_{gi} - T_{bl,e}} \quad (A.6)$$

- Convective and film cooling:

$$W^+ = \frac{1}{1 + BB} \frac{\epsilon_o - \epsilon_{fl}(1 - \eta_{cl}) - \epsilon_o \epsilon_{fl} \eta_{cl}}{\eta_{cl}(1 - \epsilon_o)} \quad (A.7)$$

In Eq. (A.7), BB is defined as,

$$BB = \left(Bi_{TBC} - \frac{\epsilon_o - \epsilon_{fl}}{1 - \epsilon_o} \cdot Bi_{met} \right) \quad (A.8)$$

- Transpiration cooling [35]:

$$W^+ = \ln[1/(1 - \epsilon_o)] \quad (A.9)$$

With W^+ , we can be able to calculate the required cooling air ratio for the blade row,

$$\xi = \frac{\dot{m}_{tbc}}{\dot{m}_{gi}} = KW^+ \quad (A.10)$$

where K is a constant indicating the cooling flow factor.

Few parameters can be assumed as a constant value as in Table A.6 instead of calculating manually. The constant values are taken from [17,36].

With the calculation of bleed mass flow and the temperature difference ratio, the change in stagnation temperature across turbine with cooling can be solved using the energy conservation equation, Eq. (31). The various values of c_p were computed using shock detonation tool-box [26].

Table A.6

Cooling parameters for 0-D models.

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
ϵ_{fl}	0.4	η_{cl}	70%
Bi_{TBC}	0.3	Bi_{met}	0.15
K	0.045	T_{bl}	1100K

Fig. B.18. Pressure decay behind the detonation front [25].

Appendix B. RDC model

The function $f(\sigma)$ can be taken from the graph of Sichel and Foster [25] experimental values of the pressure decay behind the detonation front.

Fig. B.18 shows the pressure decay as a function of P_{CJ} and σ where σ varies from 0 to 2.90. The function $f(\sigma)$ can be calculated using a fifth order polynomial function from Fig. B.18, which is given in Eq. (B.1).

$$f(\sigma) = 0.0282\sigma^5 - 0.2604\sigma^4 + 0.8681\sigma^3 - 1.1357\sigma^2 + 0.0623\sigma + 0.9988 = \frac{P(\theta)}{P_{CJ}} \quad (B.1)$$

where $\sigma = \frac{\theta_{det} - \theta}{\eta_{det}}$ and θ are the points in the expansion zone as in Fig. 3(a).

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